

OBJECT AND SUBJECTS OF INNOVATION ACTIVITY

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Abstract: Investors themselves have the right to choose one or more areas of innovation activity. No one can force them to choose a field of activity or objects of innovation. Investors themselves make decisions about choosing a particular area and investing in innovations in a certain area. Subjects of innovation activity can be one investor, several investor-participants carrying out entrepreneurial and other activities.

Key words: Innovation, innovation activity, objects of innovation, subjects of innovation, modernization, investments, capital investments.

Its objects and subjects participate in the organization of innovation activities. Subjects of innovation are physical and legal entities and the state that have property and intellectual assets participating in innovation activities. The relations between the subjects of innovation have the nature of production. The subjects of innovation activity are: investors, customers, contractors, users of capital investment facilities, etc.

Innovative activity providers

Investors make capital investments using their own funds or borrowed funds. Legal and natural persons or their association, state bodies and foreign legal and natural persons can be investors.

Investors have equal rights to:

- in the implementation of innovation activities in the form of capital investments;

- independent determination of the volume and directions of capital investments, as well as in concluding contracts with other subjects of innovation activity;
- ownership, use and disposal of objects created and purchased at the expense of capital investments;
- implementation of capital investments and transfer of the right to its results to legal entities and individuals, state and local authorities through a contract or state contract;
- to combine own and attracted funds with funds of other investors to implement joint capital investments on the basis of signed contracts;
- control over the appropriate use of capital investment funds.

Customers are legal entities and individuals represented by investors for the implementation of investment projects. At the same time, they do not interfere in the business activities of innovation activity subjects. Investors themselves can appear as customers. Customers who are not investors will have the right to own, use and dispose of capital investments in the manner and period specified in the contract.

Contractors are legal entities and individuals who perform work on the basis of contracts concluded by customers. Contractors must have a permit (license) to carry out construction and assembly work. Licensing of construction activities is carried out in order to protect the rights of consumers of construction products.

Users of capital investment facilities are legal entities and individuals, as well as state bodies, local authorities, foreign countries, international organizations, for which these facilities are created.

Investors can act as users of capital investment facilities. The subject of innovation activity provides an opportunity to combine two or more of its

functions. Subjects of innovation activity must fulfill the requirements set by state bodies and use capital investments in a targeted manner.

Innovation activity is related to the fields chosen by the investor, as well as the goals for which innovation should be spent, that is, the objects of innovation.

According to innovations, participation in production and consumption work, the following objects of innovation activity can be distinguished:

- newly created and modernized (updated) fixed assets and working capital in all sectors of the national economy;
- scientific and technical products, research, teaching, training and retraining of personnel;
- intellectual property, authorship, invention, discovery rights, experience;
- high-value securities, target funds;
- other property objects;
- property rights.

It is forbidden to direct investments for tools that cannot be created and used, that do not meet ecological and other norms, sanitary and hygienic requirements, prohibited by laws and regulations, and these works cannot be the object of spending innovations. It is also forbidden to spend innovations for activities that harm the legal interests of citizens, legal entities and the state.

It is possible to create a group of objects of innovation activity based on the spheres of attracting and spending innovations.

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